

Structural Studies on Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(III), Cr(III) and VO(II) Chelates of Some Methyl Substituted 2-Hydroxyacetophenonethiosemicarbazones

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Chelates of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(III), Cr(III) and VO(II), with 2-hydroxyacetophenonethiosemicarbazone and its 3,4 and 5-methyl derivatives have been prepared. All these chelates have been characterized on the basis of their analytical, infrared, electronic spectral, magnetic and conductivity data. All chelates except Cu(II) and Co(II) chelates are found to have octahedral structures. Cu(II) chelates are square-planar in nature. Co(II) chelates may have five coordination.

THE chelating properties of thiosemicarbazones containing ONS donor sequence are well established. As these ligands show useful analytical applications as well as biological activities, coordination chemists have taken a keen interest in the study of thiosemicarbazones as potential ligands.

The present report describes the isolation of chelates of 2-hydroxyacetophenonethiosemicarbazone (hat H₂), 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-acetophenonethiosemicarbazone (3mhat H₂), 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-acetophenonethiosemicarbazone (4mhat H₂) and 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenonethiosemicarbazone (5mhat H₂) with Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(III), Cr(III) and VO(II). Their probable structures have been determined on the basis of their elemental, magnetic, conductivity, electronic and infrared spectral measurements.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of reagent grade. In the preparation of metal chelates of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Fe(III) metal chlorides were used. Vanadyl sulphate and chromium nitrate were used to prepare VO(II) and Cr(III) chelates respectively. All the ligands used were prepared by literature method¹.

Preparation of complexes: Cu(II) and Fe(III) complexes were prepared by directly mixing required quantities of ligand and metal solutions in ethanol. Ni(II) complexes were isolated after refluxing the reaction mixture for 1 hr. VO(II) and Co(II) complexes were obtained as above in presence of 1 g sodium acetate. Cr(III) complexes were isolated after refluxing the reaction mixture for 4 hrs in presence of 1 g sodium acetate.

All physico-chemical measurements were made as described earlier².

Results and Discussion

The analytical and conductivity data are presented in Table 1. Molar conductivities of Fe(III) and Ni(II) chelates suggest their 1:1 and 1:2 electrolytic nature respectively. The molar conductivity of Cu(II) and

Cr(III) complexes in ethanol is fairly large, so that possibility of ionization cannot be ruled out. However, the residual conductivities observed may be attributed to partial solvolysis of metal complexes³. Rest of the complexes are non-electrolytes.

The ligands used in the present study can take any of the following two forms (I) or (Ia)

(I)

R = H, hat H₂
R = 3Me, 3mhat H₂
R = 4Me, 4mhat H₂
R = 5Me, 5mhat H₂

(II)

R = H, hat H
R = 3Me, 3mhat H
R = 4Me, 4mhat H
R = 5Me, 5mhat H

(Ia)

(III)

R = H, hat
R = 3Me, 3mhat
R = 4Me, 4mhat
R = 5Me, 5mhat

The infrared spectral data are given in Table 2. The infrared spectra of the ligands show an intense strong ν_{C-S} band at $\sim 850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and no band due to ν_{S-H} near 2570 cm^{-1} , which indicates that the ligands remain in thione form (I) at least in the solid state⁴. However, in solution it is likely to be in equilibrium with the thio tautomeric form (Ia). All the ligands show two ν_{N-H} bands at 3250 and 3325 cm^{-1} which do not undergo any appreciable shift on complex formation indicating non-coordination of NH_2 group. The ν_{OH} bands at $3000-3120\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of the ligands

disappear in complexes other than those of Ni(II) indicating the removal of hydroxy proton. In Ni(II) complexes the appearance of ν_{OH} band at approximately the same position as in ligands suggest the coordination of OH group to the metal ion as otherwise the cleavage of hydrogen bonding in the ligands on complexation should have resulted in the upward shift of the band. The downward shift of the C=S band in the ligands by 20-60 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Fe(III) and Cr(III) suggests the coordi-

nation of the metal ion through sulphur atom of the C=S group^{6,7} of I or II. However, this band suffers a large lowering by 90-120 cm^{-1} in the complexes of VO(II) and Co(II) suggesting the presence of C-S-M formed through the deprotonation of the OH and SH groups of (Ia) to yield the divalent ligand anion(III) which is also consistent with the appearance of medium intensity ν_{N-H} band at 960 cm^{-1} associated with the donation of $N^{2'}-N^{3'}$ band at the formation of C=N^{2'} band^{8,9}.

TABLE 1—DECOMPOSITION TEMP., ANALYSES, MAGNETIC, IR AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA

Compound	Decomp. Temp.	Found (Calcd.)%			μ_{eff} (B.M.) obs. (Calcd.)	Molar conductance $\text{Ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$	IR (cm^{-1})		
		M	S	Cl			ν_{CN}^+	$\nu_{\text{NH}_2}^+$	$\nu_{\text{C=S}}$
hat H ₂	—	—	—	—	—	—	1490s,s		830 s,s
[Cu(hatH)Cl]	195	21.05	10.46	11.89	1.41	25.10	1300s,m		
[Ni(hatH ₂) ₂]Cl ₂	215	10.87	11.77	13.06	2.95	58.80	1450s,m		780 s,s
[Co(hat). 3H ₂ O]	260	17.92	9.62	—	2.60	1.96	1310 sh,m		
[Fe(hatH)Cl. 2H ₂ O]Cl	250	14.66	8.40	18.60	5.93	32.66	1480s,s		740 s,s
Cr(hatH) ₂	320	8.05	13.69	—	3.90	28.25	1390s,m		
VO(hat)H ₂ O	145	16.68	10.35	—	1.45	4.08	1450s,s		790 s,s
3mhat H ₂	—	—	—	—	—	—	1315a,m		
[Cu(3mhatH)Cl]	175	19.80	9.96	11.43	1.04	22.00	1470s,s		800 s,s
[Ni(3mhatH ₂) ₂]Cl ₂	220	10.35	11.36	11.85	2.87	61.20	1300s,s		
[Co(3mhat). 3H ₂ O]	281	17.08	9.32	—	2.61	1.72	1450s,s		740 s,s
[Fe(3mhatH)Cl. 2H ₂ O]Cl	228	14.40	8.23	17.95	6.04	33.76	1320s,m		
Cr(3mhatH) ₂	260	7.62	12.50	—	3.98	24.92	1450s,m		840 s,s
VO(3mhat)H ₂ O	155	16.45	10.12	—	1.39	4.08	1310s,s		
4mhat H ₂	—	—	—	—	—	—	1445s,s		850 s,s
[Cu(4mhatH)Cl]	165	19.67	9.73	11.13	1.30	28.20	1290s,m		
[Ni(4mhatH ₂) ₂]Cl ₂	208	10.31	11.49	12.48	3.01	61.20	1450s,s		840 sh,m
[Co(4mhat). 3H ₂ O]	271	17.29	9.28	—	2.66	2.11	1330 s,m		
[Fe(4mhatH)Cl. 2H ₂ O]Cl	245	14.35	8.43	17.82	5.87	33.91	1400 s,m		850 s,m
Cr(4mhatH) ₂	240	7.51	12.55	—	3.81	20.40	1340 s,s		
VO(4mhat)H ₂ O	170	16.38	10.05	—	1.30	2.82	1450 s,m		780 s,m
5mhat H ₂	—	—	—	—	—	—	1390 s,m		
[Cu(5mhatH)Cl]	185	20.21	9.72	11.01	1.49	29.80	1460 s,s		830 s,m
[Ni(5mhatH ₂) ₂]Cl ₂	212	10.23	10.90	12.53	2.92	56.50	1320 s,s		
[Co(5mhat). 3H ₂ O]	255	17.22	9.35	—	2.76	3.76	1440 s,m		850 s,s
[Fe(5mhatH)Cl. 2H ₂ O]Cl	235	14.56	8.40	17.76	5.84	33.96	1310 s,s		
Cr(5mhatH) ₂	290	7.75	12.63	—	4.01	15.50	1450 s,s		770 s,m
VO(5mhat)H ₂ O	180	16.73	10.18	—	1.41	4.39	1360 s,m		810 s,s
		(16.63)	(10.46)				1450 s,m		760 s,br
							1390 s,s		

s,s=sharp strong, s,m=sharp medium, sh,m=shoulder medium, sh,w=shoulder weak, m=medium, s,br=sharp broad,

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC REFLECTANCE DATA OF COMPLEXES OF Ni(II), Co(II), Cr(III), Fe(III) AND VO(II)

Compound	Electronic transitions ^a				B ₃₅	β ₃₅	δv	10 Dq	λ
	ν ₁	ν ₂	ν ₃	ν ₄					
[Ni(hat H ₂) ₂]Cl ₂	11110	17090	25000	—	583.9	0.540	± 610	11110	-87.92
[Ni(3mhat H ₂) ₂]Cl ₂	11110	16660	25310	—	575.9	0.5327	+232	11110	-62.56
[Ni(4mhat H ₂) ₂]Cl ₂	11110	17240	24390	—	553.1	0.512	± 940	11110	-63.81
[Ni(5mhat H ₂) ₂]Cl ₂	11500	16660	24390	—	436.0	0.403	± 754	11500	-58.03
[Co(hat). 3H ₂ O]	9757	20410	22730	—	—	—	—	—	—
[Co(3mhat). 3H ₂ O]	9616	20200	22990	—	—	—	—	—	—
[Co(4mhat). 3H ₂ O]	9434	20410	22990	—	—	—	—	—	—
[Co(5mhat). 3H ₂ O]	9260	20410	22730	—	—	—	—	—	—
Cr(hat H) ₃	17240	23810	37693 ^b	—	637.0	0.6923	—	17240	62.74
Cr(3mhat H) ₃	17390	24100	37640 ^b	—	678.9	0.7379	—	17390	62.47
Cr(4mhat H) ₃	17540	24100	38350 ^b	—	669.4	0.7276	—	17540	64.43
Cr(5mhat H) ₃	17850	23810	37962 ^b	—	571.0	0.6405	—	17850	47.77
[Fe(hat H)Cl. 2H ₂ O]Cl	15630	18520	22730	26670	—	—	—	—	—
[Fe(3mhat H)Cl. 2H ₂ O]Cl	15880	18520	22220	27003	—	—	—	—	—
[Fe(4mhat H)Cl. 2H ₂ O]Cl	15630	18520	22990	26310	—	—	—	—	—
[Fe(5mhat H)Cl. 2H ₂ O]Cl	15380	17850	22220	26030	—	—	—	—	—
[VO(hat)H ₂ O]	11110	16000	20430	—	—	—	—	—	—
[VO(3mhat)H ₂ O]	10920	15880	20480	—	—	—	—	—	—
[VO(4mhat). H ₂ O]	10990	15630	20620	—	—	—	—	—	—
[VO(5mhat). H ₂ O]	11110	16310	20620	—	—	—	—	—	—

a) For Ni(II) ν₁ = ⁴A_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F), ν₂ = ⁴A_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(F) and ν₃ = ⁴A_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P);
 Co(II) assignment of transitions for the low spin complexes is not possible;
 Cr(III) ν₁ = ⁴A_{2g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F), ν₂ = ⁴A_{2g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(F) and ν₃ = ⁴A_{2g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P);
 Fe(III) ν₁ = ⁶A_{1g} → ⁶T_{1g}, ν₂ = ⁶A_{1g} → ⁶T_{2g}, ν₃ = ⁶A_{1g} → ⁶E_g and ν₄ = ⁶A_{1g} → ⁶T_{1g}(P);
 VO(II) ν₁ = ³B₂ → ³E, ν₂ = ³B₂ → ³B₁ and ν₃ = ³B₂ → ³A₁⁰.

b) Calculated value of ν₃.

All ligands show two moderately strong bands at 1490 and 1300 cm⁻¹ assigned as ν_{CN} + α_{NH2} + ν_{CS}¹⁰. It has been assumed that the 1490 and 1300 cm⁻¹ bands possess a higher contribution of ν_{C=S} and ν_{C-N} components respectively². On complex formation the former band shifts to lower energy while the latter shifts to higher energy. However, exceptionally higher value of 1390 cm⁻¹ only in the Co(II) and VO(II) complexes is in conformity with the proposed existence of the ligand as bivalent anion(III). The absorption bands at 1240 cm⁻¹(ν_{CN} + ν_{CS}) and 1160 and 1000 cm⁻¹(ν_{NH2} + β_{NH2}) are only slightly affected on complex formation. The downward shift of strong and sharp ν_{C=N}³ band of the azo-methine group¹² at 1580 cm⁻¹ by 10-40 cm⁻¹ in the Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(III) and VO(II) complexes indicate the coordination through N₃^{11,12}. This also implies that all the ligands act as bidentate in the case of Cu(II) and Cr(III) complexes.

The absorption bands at 3440-3480, 1600, 520 and 720 cm⁻¹ appearing in the spectra of Fe(III), Co(II) and VO(II) complexes may be assigned as ν_{O-H}, bending, rocking and wagging modes of coordinated water respectively. A strong band at 970 cm⁻¹ in the VO(II) complexes may be due to ν_{V-O}¹⁴.

Visible reflectance spectra of Cu(II) complexes show a broad band in the range 15000-18000 cm⁻¹ which may be interpreted in terms of square planar stereochemistry. Absence of any band below 10,000 cm⁻¹ eliminates the possibility of tetrahedral or pseudotetrahedral environment in these complexes^{15,16}. The subnormal room temperature μ_{eff} values (Table 1) of all the Cu(II) complexes may be explained in terms of metal-metal interaction¹⁷ in the dimers¹⁸ formed through halogen bridging¹⁹ resulting in the formation of [CuOSCl₂] chromophore.

Nickel(II) complexes show three bands in their reflectance spectra (Table 2) favouring an octahedral stereochemistry²⁰. The proposed assignment of these bands are consistent with the required ν₃/ν₁ ratio of 1.44-1.55²¹. The observed bands have been utilized to obtain important ligand field parameters (Table 2). Considerable reduction of B₃₅ values of the free ion from 1041 cm⁻¹ to 436-580 cm⁻¹ on complex formation indicates the appreciable covalent character of the metal ligand bonds. An approximate value of spin orbit coupling constant λ has been obtained for each complex from λ = 2.7 × B₃₅²/10 Dq using average value of B₃₅²². The experimental room temperature μ_{eff} values lie in the range required for octahedral stereochemistry and are in good agreement with the values calculated by substituting the experimental 10 Dq and λ values in the relationship μ_{eff} = μ_{s.o} (1 - 4λ/10 Dq)²⁴.

Experimental μ_{eff} values of 2.60-2.76 BM for all the Co(II) complexes favour spin pairing indicating, either four (square planar) or five coordination around the metal ion²⁵. However, the rich reflectance spectra with bands around 5000, 15000, 20000 and 23000 cm⁻¹ rule out the square planar stereochemistry and support the five coordination. The five coordination in these complexes may be justified if two of the three water molecules are assumed to act as coordinated and the third as lattice water.

The bands observed in the reflectance spectra of Fe(III) complexes are very weak and may be assigned to spin forbidden transitions (Table 2) under octahedral stereochemistry which is supported by the observed room temperature μ_{eff} values of 5.92 BM^{26,27}.

The reflectance spectra of Cr(III) complexes show three bands which presumably are due to d-d transitions

indicating an octahedral stereochemistry²⁸. In addition to the two higher energy bands in the region 17240-17850 (ν_1) and 23810-24100 cm^{-1} (ν_2) there is a low energy spin forbidden band at 11360-12120 cm^{-1} ²⁹. The higher energy spin allowed ν_3 transition usually occurs above 30,000 cm^{-1} which would have been obscured because of ligand absorption in this region³⁰. The ν_3 values calculated by method (a)³⁰ are given in Table 2. Low values of B_{35} are believed to be indicative of both σ and π type delocalization²⁹. An attempt has been made to calculate the spin-orbit coupling constant using $\lambda = 0.0110 (B_{35} + 1.080)^3 + 0.0062^{31}$. The values for the covalency parameters have also been calculated as $\lambda/90^{31}$. The results are given in Table 2. The room temperature μ_{eff} values (Table 1) which are close to $\mu_{s.o.}$ also support the high spin octahedral structure³² proposed on the basis of reflectance spectral data.

The magnetic moments (Table 1) of the VO(II) complexes are in the range 1.32-1.45 B.M. at room temperature which are abnormally lower than the spin only value of 1.73 B.M. The magnetic moments for the low-symmetry complexes are expected around 1.73 B.M. when the orbital angular contribution is almost completely quenched³³. These subnormal values may be due to the presence of exchanged coupled antiferromagnetism³⁴. There are several reports indicating subnormal magnetic moments for the VO(II) complexes suggesting binuclear structure for the complexes³⁵⁻³⁷. In the present study the complexes may have attained the following binuclear structure :

The three bands observed in their reflectance spectra may be assigned in an octahedral symmetry with tetragonal distortion³⁸.

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